

Eclipse mapping study of the eclipsing binary KIC 3858884 with hybrid δ Sct/ γ Dor component

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ABSTRACT

Aims. Pulsating stars in eclipsing binary systems offer a unique possibility to empirically identify pulsation modes using the geometric effect of the eclipses on the pulsation signals. Here we explore the δ Scuti type pulsations in the eclipsing binary system KIC 3858884 with the aim of identifying the dominant modes using various photometric methods.

Methods. We used the *Kepler* short cadence photometry data. Refined binary model and pulsation parameters were determined using an iterative separation of the eclipsing binary and pulsation signals. We used the photometric residuals, a phase modulation study, and a double eclipse mapping to identify the host stars of the dominant pulsations. Échelle diagram diagnostics were employed to locate the frequencies with the most influence from the eclipses. Direct Fitting methods assuming spherical harmonic surface patterns were explored to determine an orientation for the symmetry axis and to infer surface mode numbers ℓ and m . Ancillary mode number estimates were obtained from reconstructions of general surface patterns using Dynamic Eclipse Mapping. The use of these methods allowed mode identifications independent from asteroseismic models.

Results. We unambiguously established the secondary star as the main source of the pulsations. Seven peaks were found to show pronounced modulations during the secondary eclipses. For the first time, we could detect two hidden modes with amplitude intensification during the eclipses. Only one additional frequency appears to originate from the primary. Direct Fitting results point to an essentially aligned pulsation axis for the secondary. We successfully reconstructed surface patterns and determined mode numbers for most of the selected frequencies with both of our methods. One radial and three sectoral modes, (1,-1), (2, \pm 2) and (3, \pm 3), were found. The two strongest modes were both found to be nonradial. The hidden modes were identified as (3, \pm 1) and (2, \pm 1) respectively. One additional radial mode turned out to be a combination frequency. The partial disagreement between the results of the two methods may indicate that either the strongest modes deviate from strict spherical harmonics, or that the pulsation axis cannot be constrained by the photometric data alone. Future spectroscopic observations could help in resolving the question.

Key words. asteroseismology – binaries: eclipsing – stars: individual: KIC 3858884 – stars: oscillations

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Table A.1: First 55 detected frequencies with the highest amplitude.

id	$f (f_{\text{orb}})$	$f (d^{-1})$	amp	φ (rad)	note
F1	187.65	7.2245	0.009821	2.69	
F2	193.95	7.4671	0.009052	4.87	
F3	255.30	9.8292	0.001868	0.30	
F4	194.96	7.5061	0.001801	2.45	F2 + f_{orb}
F5	174.81	6.7301	0.001550	2.72	
F6	247.04	9.5111	0.001243	3.10	
F7	381.60	14.6916	0.001182	0.88	F1 + F2
F8	304.31	11.7158	0.001009	5.56	
F9	382.15	14.7128	0.000593	0.71	
F10	191.08	7.3564	0.000539	3.59	
F11	193.65	7.4555	0.000485	2.34	
F12	382.80	14.7378	0.000458	6.13	
F13	187.95	7.2361	0.000512	2.02	
F14	1.00	0.0385	0.000432	2.60	f_{orb}
F15	235.49	9.0665	0.000335	5.02	3 · F12 – 3 · F8
F16	18.11	0.6972	0.000406	0.12	
F17	188.59	7.2607	0.000348	2.30	
F18	208.49	8.0268	0.000370	0.42	
F19	253.46	9.7581	0.000364	4.72	
F20	368.91	14.2031	0.000329	2.37	
F21	298.89	11.5074	0.000317	3.96	
F22	259.55	9.9926	0.000323	3.85	3 · F13 – F8
F23	6.30	0.2426	0.000291	2.14	F2 – F1
F24	241.44	9.2956	0.000271	2.29	
F25	186.42	7.1770	0.000258	4.14	
F26	442.95	17.0537	0.000262	2.61	F1 + F3
F27	375.30	14.4491	0.000279	4.92	2 · F1
F28	387.90	14.9341	0.000241	3.00	2 · F2
F29	23.41	0.9013	0.000230	1.07	
F30	268.39	10.3331	0.000238	5.66	
F31	240.81	9.2712	0.000245	2.97	
F32	359.01	13.8220	0.000220	0.82	
F33	440.99	16.9781	0.000213	1.38	F2 + F6
F34	368.76	14.1972	0.000203	1.53	F2 + F5
F35	13.24	0.5097	0.000186	1.85	4 · F17 – 3 · F6
F36	367.34	14.1426	0.000213	4.53	
F37	180.72	6.9579	0.000221	1.62	
F38	443.91	17.0904	0.000295	4.42	F3 + F17
F39	305.54	11.7633	0.000252	2.02	
F40	382.67	14.7326	0.000173	5.84	
F41	236.77	9.1156	0.000183	5.67	
F42	388.91	14.9732	0.000174	0.68	2 · F2 + f_{orb}
F43	186.95	7.1976	0.000172	5.66	F13 – f_{orb}
F44	194.69	7.4956	0.000144	5.05	
F45	293.12	11.2849	0.000159	5.44	
F46	311.03	11.9745	0.000269	3.85	3 · F29 + F31
F47	177.80	6.8452	0.000150	5.38	F5 + 3 · f_{orb}
F48	161.82	6.2301	0.000147	2.54	
F49	3.04	0.1172	0.000148	0.64	
F50	27.35	1.0531	0.000147	5.47	
F51	311.02	11.9741	0.000226	5.38	
F52	188.91	7.2729	0.000182	1.37	
F53	296.52	11.4161	0.000142	1.55	
F54	13.14	0.5057	0.000140	0.30	F13 – F5
F55	61.35	2.3621	0.000138	1.92	F3 – F2

Notes. The associated frequencies in both units of orbital frequencies and c/d, the amplitude and phases are presented. In the last column the possible frequency combination is indicated as well.